

Development of a Geospatial Alumni Database and Web Application

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Abstract—This report details the development of a cloud-hosted university alumni database integrating geospatial mapping and professional data to facilitate networking. The application relies on a Python and Flask backend connected to a NoSQL Firestore database. It allows authenticated users to explore a directory of university alumni filtered by geographic location, graduation year, and professional role. The project used an iterative, full-stack methodology to successfully deploy a functional prototype and evaluate both automated and manual deployment strategies.

I. INTRODUCTION

Establishing connections between current students and alumni supports workforce development and academic mentorship. The original problem domain was proposed by the Undergraduate Research Program to address the need for a centralized platform that would enable current students to locate and contact alumni at specific organizations for interviews and professional guidance. This project created a web application to visualize the geographic distribution of the University of Wisconsin–Whitewater (UWW) computer science alumni. The application integrates professional information from LinkedIn with the Google Maps JavaScript API, implementing full-stack software development, automated testing, and continuous deployment.

II. FINANCIAL SUMMARY

The project was funded by a \$1,500 UWW College of Letters and Sciences Mini-Grant. The original budget allocated \$500 for the undergraduate research stipend, \$400 for cloud hosting, \$300 for API usage, \$100 for domain registration and related DNS costs, and \$200 for miscellaneous technical resources (e.g., software licenses, literature). Actual expenditures totaled \$500 — utilized entirely for the undergraduate research stipend. The remaining \$1,000 budget was preserved because cloud hosting, database storage, and API access remained within the complimentary tiers provided by the Google Cloud Platform and external mapping services. The planned domain registration and miscellaneous software costs were ultimately deemed unnecessary for the initial prototype deployment.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Development followed an iterative, full-stack methodology, shipping features in distinct layers — e.g., foundational CRUD operations for database population/aggregation, API services, and user interfaces — to ensure continuous local deployability and mitigate integration failures. The database architecture transitioned from the initially proposed PostgreSQL normalized schema to a NoSQL document model utilizing Google Cloud Firestore, which better accommodated the variable data structures inherent in professional networking profiles.

The web service operates on Python and Flask, served by Unicorn, and is containerized with Docker for deployment on Google Cloud Run. Google Cloud Storage is utilized to manage static assets, system secrets, and images. Asynchronous operations, including delayed notifications and job status tracking, are handled via Google Cloud Tasks integrated with Firestore. The frontend interface utilizes Jinja templates, Flask-Assets, and JavaScript to render an interactive map and a searchable list view. User authentication is strictly enforced through Flask-Dance, Flask-Login, and OAuth protocols linked to existing professional networking accounts (i.e., LinkedIn). System reliability was verified using automated pytest suites targeting filter functionality and URL normalization, alongside rigorous manual integration testing.

IV. DATA COLLECTION AND LIMITATIONS

The initial design included automated web scraping to populate the database with publicly available professional records. Early iterations utilized the BeautifulSoup (Python) library before transitioning to custom Playwright scrapers to handle dynamic web content and JavaScript rendering. However, continuous automated data ingestion proved unfeasible in production. The target professional networking platform (LinkedIn) actively blocks programmatic access, detecting anomalous traffic originating from static IP addresses and consistent credential sets. Even after extending request intervals to 30–60 seconds, recurring session invalidations and authentication failures persisted. Resolving these blocks via the platform's enterprise API, as well as integrating profile verification, requires formal corporate registration (e.g., an LLC) — which falls outside the scope of this project. Consequently, scraping capabilities were restricted to manual, administrator-triggered updates to prevent service account termination.

V. APPLICATION FEATURES

The deployed web application provides both geospatial map and list views of the alumni directory (see [fig. 1](#) and [fig. 2](#), respectively), allowing users to filter records by graduation class, degree, employer, and profile verification status. Security and privacy parameters are built directly into the data layer. Identifying information, specifically alumni surnames, remains obscured to unauthorized users and authenticated strangers until the system verifies their distinct affiliation with the University of Wisconsin–Whitewater, either through automated profile parsing or manual administrative overrides.

The system features a robust administrative console (see [fig. 3](#)) that allows authorized users to process incoming data ingestion requests by targeting specific profile URLs. Scraped accounts enter a “proposed” state; upon subsequent user login, the application prompts the alumni to confirm or modify their aggregated data (see [fig. 4](#)). Additionally, the console enables administrators to approve user profile modifications and dispatch targeted batch communications and notifications using Flask-Mail.

VI. CONCLUSION

The application is currently live and accessible at <https://alumbd.danielszelogowski.com/>. It functions as an accessible, localized directory for the target demographic despite the strict constraints on automated data aggregation. The codebase is version-controlled and extensively documented, allowing future developers to take over maintenance and enabling easy replication to potentially scale the project across multiple universities. Future work will focus on migrating data ingestion to the enterprise API once organizational credentials become available. Additional system optimizations are required to resolve notification delays inherent to the current Google Tasks implementation and to mitigate sporadic “Service Unavailable” HTTP errors triggered by Cloud Run instance cold starts during traffic spikes.

Fig. 2. Alumni Directory List View and Administrative Processing

Fig. 3. Administrative Console Detailing Scraped Profile Fields

Fig. 1. Interactive Map Interface for Alumni Location Visualization

Fig. 4. Authenticated User Profile and Modification Interface